

Original article

Unlocking Early Diagnosis: Using Liver FABP-1 to Reveal Subclinical Renal Damage in Type 2 Diabetes

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Background: Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a heterogeneous metabolic disease in which the main finding is chronic hyperglycemia.. Diabetic nephropathy (DN) is the leading cause of end-stage renal failure and increases the risk of cardiovascular disease. Liver fatty acid protein (L - FABP), also known as FABP1, is an intracellular fatty acid expressed in the liver and kidneys. Current diagnostic markers, such as albuminuria and serum creatinine levels, often fail to identify DN at its initial stages, necessitating the exploration of novel biomarkers. One such promising biomarker is Fatty Acid-Binding Protein 1 (FABP1), also known as liver-type fatty acid-binding protein (L-FABP), which has shown potential in the early detection of DN in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) patient. The aim of the study is to investigate the role of fatty acid binding protein -1 as a predictive marker for early detection of diabetic nephropathy in type 2 diabetes.

Methodology: About 60 study participants were selected from the General Medicine OPD based on the age and gender matched depending on the on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. All the biochemical parameters were analysed by using biochemistry auto analyser and FABP-1 by sandwich ELISA method.

Results: ROC curve for Fatty acid binding protein cut off sensitivity and specificity with area under curve values for group 1 T2DM as 0.2426,0.683 and 0.371 and nephropathy as 0.24005,0.707and 0.68 respectively.

Conclusion: Higher levels of serum L-FABP was associated with increased risk of renal function decline in patients with T2DM and renal dysfunction. FABP1 found to be as a potential of predictive biomarker.

Key Words: Fatty Acid Binding Protein (FABP), Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), Diabetic Nephropathy (DN), Diabetic Kidney Disease (DKD)

INTRODUCTION: Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a heterogeneous metabolic disease in which the main finding is chronic hyperglycemia. [1] The cause of insulin secretion is reduced: or reduced insulin action. In diabetes, chronic hyperglycemia is associated with long-term damage, dysfunction, and failure of various organs, particularly the eyes, kidneys, nerves, heart, and blood vessels.[2]

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is the leading cause of chronic kidney disease (CKD). Diabetic nephropathy (DN) is the leading cause of end-stage renal failure and increases the risk of cardiovascular disease. Early diagnostic markers for predicting and monitoring the progression of Diabetic nephropathy (DN) are needed to enable the timely administration of the most appropriate protective treatments of CKD [3].

Liver fatty acid protein (L - FABP), also known as FABP1, is an intracellular fatty acid expressed in the liver and kidneys. In the kidney, L-FABP expression is mainly localized in the proximal tubules. Similar study previously proposed that the elevated L-FABP level is associated with interstitial damage in the renal tubules, such that excess free fatty acid uptake into the proximal tubules causes interstitial damage. [4]

Liver-type fatty acid-binding protein (L-FABP) is emerging as an excellent biomarker in plasma in early prediction of CKD [5]. Patients with CKD are at a high risk of cardiovascular disease and mortality and are associated with increased treatment costs [6]. The diabetes epidemic has resulted in diabetic nephropathy becoming the most frequent cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) in most countries.

Diabetic nephropathy is a severe complication occurring in diabetic patients and it is associated with an increased risk of all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease and progression to end stage renal disease (ESRD), requiring costly renal replacement therapy in the form of dialysis or transplantation. Diabetic nephropathy is a syndrome characterized by the presence of pathological quantities of urine albumin excretion, diabetic glomerular lesions, and loss of glomerular filtration rate (GFR) in diabetics.[7]Tubulointerstitial injury

has been suggested to have an important impact on the progression of diabetic nephropathy[8]

Fatty acid-binding protein 1 (FABP1) (also known as liver-type fatty acid-binding protein or L-FABP) is a 14 kDa small molecule that is expressed in the proximal tubules of the human kidney and participates in fatty acid metabolism [9] In addition, a clinical study reported associations between the urinary excretion of FABP1 and the severity of tubulointerstitial damage and rate of chronic kidney disease (CKD) progression in patients with non-diabetic CKD[10]

Diabetic nephropathy is characterized by progressive albuminuria, declining glomerular filtration rate (GFR), and histopathological changes such as glomerulosclerosis and tubulointerstitial fibrosis (Magee et al., 2017). Traditional markers for DN, such as albuminuria and serum creatinine levels, often fail to detect early renal damage, leading to a need for more sensitive biomarkers. FABP1 is primarily expressed in the liver and proximal renal tubules, where it regulates fatty acid transport and protects against lipid-induced kidney injury[11].

Studies suggest that elevated urinary and plasma FABP1 levels correlate with kidney damage in T2DM patients before the onset of albuminuria [12]. This makes FABP1 a potential early predictive marker for DN, allowing for timely intervention and management strategies to slow disease progression.

Diabetes mellitus is a growing global health concern, affecting millions of individuals and leading to severe complications, including diabetic nephropathy (DN). DN is the leading cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) worldwide and is characterized by progressive loss of kidney function due to prolonged hyperglycemia and associated metabolic disturbances [13]. Early detection of DN is crucial for timely therapeutic intervention to prevent irreversible kidney damage. Current diagnostic markers, such as albuminuria and serum creatinine levels, often fail to identify DN at its initial stages, necessitating the exploration of novel biomarkers. One such promising biomarker is Fatty Acid-Binding Protein 1 (FABP1), also known as liver-type fatty acid-binding protein (L-FABP), which has shown potential in the early detection of DN in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) patient.

Materials and Methodology

This study was conducted at Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute (MGMCRI), in the Department of Biochemistry in collaboration with the Department of General Medicine, under the jurisdiction of Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth, Puducherry. This study was approved by the Institutional Research Council (IRC) and Institutional of Human Ethical Committee (IHEC).

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

T2DM with and without Nephropathy patients with confirmation of urinary dipstick positive for albumin subjects with age of 35-65 years irrespective of gender will be taken from General medicine OPD, followed obtaining written informed consent from the study participants. 4ml of venous blood will be collected under aseptic precautions and medical supervision.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

People with any acute and chronic illness (except T2DM and Nephropathy), gastrointestinal disorders, pregnancy, urinary tract infection and dyslipidemia

BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS

Fasting blood glucose was estimated by glucose oxidase peroxidase method (GOD/POD), fasting insulin by automated chemiluminescence; HbA1C by HPLC method. Lipid profile: Triacylglycerols in serum were measured by glycerol kinase method; Total cholesterol by enzymatic method; HDL cholesterol by polyanion precipitation. LDL cholesterol computed by Friedwald equation. $LDL\ cholesterol = total\ cholesterol - (HDL\ cholesterol + VLDL)$, where $VLDL = TAG/5$. Small dense LDL particles was quantitated using the surrogate marker (TAG/HDL) and Liver functions (Total protein and Albumin by Biuret method, AST,ALT and ALP enzymatic method, Bilirubin levels were estimated by chemiluminescence method in biochemistry auto analyser. Fatty Acid Binding Proteins -1 assay performed by sandwich ELISA method.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

MS Excel was used to record the data set. JASP-16.0 was used for statistical analysis namely, percentages that was computed for categorial variables. Mean and standard deviation was calculated for numerical variables. Independent t-test was used to determine the significance between the mean values of two groups, Mann Whitney test for non-parametric measures. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves was enabled to determine area under curve (AUC) for assessing the utility of a biochemical predictor and also a means of comparing two or more predictive models. P values

RESULT

In this study we observed higher levels of serum L-FABP was associated with increased risk of renal function decline in patients with T2DM and renal dysfunction from the following statistical tools.

An individual t - test was used to compare the data between two groups.

Table 1: Descriptive characteristics between the group and biological parameters.

Parameters	Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean	p Value
AGE	DM	41	54.73	7.727	1.207	0.047
	DM+N	41	50.95	9.143	1.428	0.047
AST	DM	41	25.02	15.712	2.454	0.028
	DM+N	41	41.51	44.397	6.934	0.029
ALT	DM	41	28.85	19.112	2.985	0.056
	DM+N	41	47.63	59.049	9.222	0.059
UREA	DM	41	31	21.526	3.362	0.046
	DM+N	41	41.85	26.776	4.182	0.047
FABP	DM	41	0.22	0.034	0.005	0.015
	DM+N	41	0.29	0.187	0.029	0.017

DM- type 2 diabetes mellitus, DM+N- type 2 diabetes mellitus with nephropathy, AST-aspartate aminotransferase, ALT-aminotransferase, FABP- Fatty acid binding protein.

Table 1 represents to significance of AST& Fatty acid binding protein among type 2 Diabetic with nephropathy, p value of 0.028(strong association) with in the parameter

p≤0.05

Table 2 : Pearson’s correlation analysis of glycemic control between T2DM and CKD subjects.

PARAMETERS	PEARSON’S r value	p VALUE
FBS vs PPBS	0.807	<0.001 [#]
FBS vs ALP	0.289	0.008 [#]
FBS vs HDL	-0.299	0.006 [#]
FBS vs VLDL	0.343	0.002 [#]

PPBS vs ALP	0.306	0.005 [#]
PPBS vs AG/RATIO	-0.245	0.026*
PPBS vs HDL	-0.324	0.003 [#]
PPBS vs VLDL	0.269	0.014*
PPBS vs TGL	0.363	< 0.001 [#]
PPBS vs TGL/HDL	0.372	< 0.001 [#]
UREA vs CREAT	0.727	< 0.001 [#]
UREA vs ALB/CREAT	-0.69	< 0.001 [#]
CREAT vs ALB/CREAT	-0.733	< 0.001 [#]

FBS- Fasting blood glucose, PPBS-Postprandial blood sugar, CREAT-Creatinine, ALP-alkaline phosphatase, ALB-Albumin ,A/G RATIO-albumin-to-globulin ratio, HDL-High-density lipoprotein, VLDL-very low density lipoprotein,TGL-triglycerides.

p ≤0.05*;

Table 3: Pearson’s correlation analysis of lipid profile between T2DM and CKD subjects.

PARAMETERS	PEARSON'S r value	p VALUE
TC vs HDL	0.46	< 0.001 [#]
TC vs LDL	0.713	< 0.001 [#]
HDL vs LDL	0.436	<0.001 [#]
HDL vs TGL	-0.446	< 0.001 [#]
HDL vs TGL/HDL	-0.732	< 0.001 [#]
LDL vs VLDL	-0.225	0.042
LDL vs TGL/HDL	-0.381	<0.001 [#]
LDL vs ALB/CREAT	0.226	0.042
VLDL vs TGL	0.633	< 0.001 [#]
VLDL vs TGL/HDL	0.57	< 0.001 [#]

TGL vs TGL/HDL	0.812	< 0.001 [#]
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TC-Total cholesterol, HDL-High-density lipoprotein, LDL-Low density lipoprotein, VLDL-very low density lipoprotein, TGL-triglycerides, CREAT-Creatinine, ALB-Albumin

$p \leq 0.05^*$;

Table 4: Pearson’s correlation analysis of liver function test between T2DM and CKD

PARAMETERS	PEARSON'S r value	p VALUE
ALP vs AGR	-0.445	< 0.001 [#]
ALP vs HDL	-0.323	0.003
ALP vs UREA	0.568	< 0.001 [#]
ALP vs CREAT	0.442	< 0.001 [#]
ALP vs TGL/HDL	0.377	< 0.001 [#]
ALP vs ALB/CREAT	-0.402	< 0.001 [#]
ALT vs AST	0.916	< 0.001 [#]
ALT vs LDL	0.437	< 0.001 [#]
AST vs TC	0.256	0.02
AST vs LDL	0.443	< 0.001 [#]
AST vs AST/ALT	-0.357	< 0.001 [#]
AGR vs UREA	-0.471	< 0.001 [#]
AGR vs CREAT	-0.471	< 0.001 [#]
AGR vs FABP	-0.245	0.027
AGR vs AST/ALT	-0.224	0.043
AG vs ALB/CREAT	0.416	< 0.001 [#]
AST/ALT vs ALB/CREAT	-0.227	0.04

ALP-alkaline phosphatase, AGR-albumin to globulin ratio, HDL-High-density lipoprotein, CREAT-Creatinine, ALB-Albumin, VLDL-very low density lipoprotein, TGL-triglycerides. TCHO-Totalcholesterol, LDL-Low density lipoprotein, AST-aspartate aminotransferase, ALT-aminotransferase.

$p \leq 0.05^*$;

Fig.1: ROC curve for Fatty acid binding protein cut off, sensitivity and specificity with area under curve values for group 1 T2DM as 0.2426, and 0.371.

Fig.2: ROC curve Fatty acid binding protein on cut off, sensitivity and specificity with area under curve values for group 2 T2DM with nephropathy as 0.24005,0.707and 0.68

DISCUSSION

Type 2 diabetes, the most common form, makes up the vast majority of these cases. A serious complication of diabetes is diabetic kidney disease (DKD), which is a leading cause of kidney failure and increases the risk of death in individuals with diabetes. Priyanka.A et.al, while albumin in the urine is a primary indicator of early DKD, it is becoming clear that kidney function can decline in diabetics even without this sign. Therefore, there is a critical need to discover new ways to treat and identify DKD earlier [14]

Diabetes is among the leading causes of kidney failure. The overall risk of dying among people with diabetes is at least double the risk of their peers without diabetes. Some of the risk factors for type 2 diabetes mellitus are physical inactivity, high-risk race/ethnicity,

women who had delivered a baby >9 lb or were diagnosed with GDM, HDL-C 250 mg/dL and hypertension ($\geq 140/90$ mm Hg or on therapy) R.Jayanthi et.al,[15] Approximately 40% of diabetic patients were affected by kidney diseases. The decreased renal function and pro inflammatory cytokines are the most important factors in determining reduction of hemoglobin levels in those patients. The inflammatory situation created by kidney disease also interferes with intestinal iron absorption and mobilization of inventories. R.Jayanthi et.al [16]

Defective insulin secretion exacerbated by insulin resistance is the cause for a plethora of metabolic aberrations observed in T2DM. Insulin mediated glucose transport in adipose tissue, skeletal muscle and cardiac muscle is the major biochemical worry that culminates in hyperglycemia. Enhanced hepatic output of glucose with associated dyslipidemia adds to the misery. AR. Srinivasan et.al [17]

In the present study, we demonstrated that plasma FABP1 levels were positively correlated with BMI, waist circumference, HOMA- β , creatinine, and FLI, and negatively correlated with albumin and eGFR. In addition, an increased plasma FABP1 concentration was associated with overt NAFLD, even in a fully adjusted model. Earlier studies have reported that hyperglycemia could act as a predisposing factor to increased low-density lipoprotein (LDL) glycation. Jayanthi R et. al [18]

Furthermore, patients in the highest (third) tertile of FABP1 were 13 times more likely to have overt NAFLD compared to those in the lowest tertile. These findings are in agreement with current evidence regarding the association between NAFLD and FABP1 [19]. Diabetic nephropathy is a major problem causing increased morbidity and mortality as the increase in total number of diabetic patients finds a reflection in increased prevalence of diabetic patients in ESRD population, and therefore identifying patients with diabetic nephropathy early is of great importance both to allow for timely interventions and to improve prognoses. Previous studies have shown that the concentration of FABP1 in urine can serve as a useful marker for the diagnosis of early-stage kidney damage, and especially acute kidney injury [20, 21]

FABP1 is a protein found in the cytoplasm of both healthy and injured proximal tubule cells in the kidneys [22]. Various pathological conditions including hyperglycemia, hypertension, proteinuria, and toxin-induced injury to the proximal tubule cells may result (either through the regulation of gene expression or directly) in an increase in the excretion of urine-derived FABP1 [23,24]

Previous studies have also demonstrated that FABP1 can play an important role in injury and repair processes in the kidneys, and that the monitoring of urine FABP1 concentration may make it possible to predict the occurrence and severity of various renal diseases [25,26]

Suzuki et al. reported that urinary FABP1 levels were significantly higher in patients with macroalbuminuria than in those with micro albuminuria [27]

It is also well known that the tubular system plays an important role in the pathophysiology of diabetic nephropathy. CKD patients have massive proteinuria and fatty acids overload in proximal tubules, and hyper triglyceridemia may also cause fatty acid overload, as well [28].

In addition, the urinary excretion of arachidonic acids and linoleic has been found to be significantly higher in CKD patients than in patients with minimal change nephrotic syndrome [29,30]

Non oxidized fatty acids appear to be cytotoxic after peroxidation, and may also provoke macrophage infiltration, the production of inflammatory factors, and accelerate the progression of tubulointerstitial damage [31]

This may explain why our diabetic nephropathy patients had high plasma FABP1 levels. In terms of CKD, animal and clinical studies have documented the usefulness of FABP1 as a marker for diabetic kidney disease. Kamijo-Ikemori et al. reported a significant increase in the expression of FABP1 in diabetic mice compared to control mice [32] In addition; Panduru et al. demonstrated that FABP1 was an indicator of the development of diabetic kidney disease in humans, regardless of its stage [33].

Many studies evaluate the L-FABP in T2DM serves as a risk factor for DKD progression and could be considered as a promising tubular marker in predicting the incidence of Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a chronic complication of diabetes, characterized by the presence of pathological quantities of urine albumin excretion and/or accompanied by a gradual deterioration in the glomerular filtration rate (GFR). It affects approximately 20-40%of patients with diabetes mellitus and is recognized as the most common cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD).Patients with CKD are at a high risk of cardiovascular disease and mortality and are associated with increased treatment costs. Although the pathogenesis of CKD remains unclear, evidence indicates that early recognition and interventions may delay the progression to ESRD and cardiovascular disease. Hence, early diagnostic markers for predicting and monitoring the progression of CKD are needed to enable the timely administration of the most appropriate protective treatments. In this study we observed higher levels of serum L-FABP was associated with increased risk of renal function decline in patients with T2DM and renal dysfunction. We suggest that in future L-FABP can be used as one of the early diagnostic marker for predicting and monitoring CKD or DKD.

LIMITATION

Small sample size is one of the limitations of the study. The present marker has not been compared with any other RFT conventional markers. Gender, duration and drug history was not taken.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, higher levels of serum L-FABP was associated with increased risk of renal function decline in patients with T2DM and renal dysfunction. Along with its role as a

metabolic risk marker, increased levels of serum L-FABP in diabetic patients may serve as a clinical marker for early progressive renal disease, which will allow early implementation of an intensive treatment in diabetic patients with nephropathy. Further studies are warranted to elucidate the role of L-FABP in the pathophysiological mechanisms involved in the development and progression of DKD.

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